

Supplementary Figure 1. Relative OTU abundances at the Phylum level. Mini blot bar from Nephela analysis showing 16S rRNA sequencing data depicting relative OTU abundance at the phylum level. Sequenced reads from cecal flushes of Naive (n=6), Vehicle (n=5), and TCDD (n=5) were uploaded into the Nephela platform for 16S OTU analysis. Individual sample bar graphs and figure legends were generated in the Nephela output files.

Supplementary Figure 2. Relative OTU abundances at the Class level. Mini blot bar from Nephel analysis showing 16S rRNA sequencing data depicting relative OTU abundance at the class level. Sequenced reads from fecal content of Naive (n=6), Vehicle (n=5), and TCDD (n=5) were uploaded into the Nephel platform for 16S OTU analysis. Individual sample bar graphs and figure legends were generated in the Nephel output files.

Supplementary Figure 6. Confirmation of microbiota depletion after ABX treatment. Naïve mice were treated with a cocktail of antibiotics for 3 weeks prior to FMT experiments. (A) UV agarose gel electrophoresis image of genomic DNA in naïve WT (n=6) and ABX mice (n=6) showing PCR expression of Eubacteria. (B) Relative normalized expression of Eubacteria in WT Naïve or ABX mice using qRT-PCR (C) UV images of culture plates with swabs from fecal samples from control (n=6), WT Naïve, and ABX mice in aerobic (top) and anaerobic conditions (bottom).

Figure S7. Effect of TCDD or FMT on MDSC induction in ABX mice. These experiments were carried out as described in Fig 2 legend. ABX (n=6 experimental per group) mice were administered TCDD alone, sodium butyrate alone, FMT from vehicle-treated (VFMT) or TCDD-treated (TFMT) donor mice. (A) Peritoneal cavity cells were stained for CD11b Gr-1 for MDSCs. (B) Total percentage of MDSCs in the ABX-treated mice given Butyrate, TCDD, and FMTs. Vertical bars show mean \pm SEM percentage of cells. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's multiple comparisons test was used to determine significance; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.